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PREREQUISITES FOR THE URBAN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE CITY OF BARNAUL, ALTAI KRAI

Abstract. *The dynamic development of domestic tourism has led to the emergence of a new trend in leisure and travel – urban tourism. The main flow of guests is aimed at visiting large destinations, but small towns form and popularize this type of tourism, focused on nearby towns and villages. In the Altai Krai and its capital, new approaches are being positioned to the awareness of the city as a tourist space and the need to build models for the development of the image of a new guest in the urban recreation industry. The authors study the dynamics of the number of tourists in the city, their target preferences and identify the places of the greatest preference of guests and travel companies offering routes around Barnaul. The purpose of the study is to identify the main trends and opportunities for the urban tourism development in the capital of the region and to develop a project concept of events aimed at a non-target audience – schoolchildren from cities and villages of the Altai Krai to increase the interest of potential investors in the development of the tourist industry of the city. The prospects for further study lie in the creation of new routes within the framework of urban tourism in the objects of the city of Barnaul.*

Keywords: *domestic tourism, city, urban tourism, tourist center, tourist destination, children's tourism, tourist services*

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ПРЕДПОСЫЛКИ РАЗВИТИЯ ГОРОДСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В ГОРОДЕ БАРНАУЛ АЛТАЙСКОГО КРАЯ

Динамичное развитие внутреннего туризма обусловило возникновение новой тенденции в отдыхе и путешествии – городского туризма. Основной поток гостей направлен на посещение крупных дестинаций, но малые города формируют и популяризируют данный вид туризма, ориентированный на близлежащие города и деревни. В Алтайском крае и его столице позиционируются новые подходы к осознанию города как туристского пространства и потребности выстраивания моделей развития образа нового гостя в городской индустрии отдыха. Изучена динамика количества туристов города, их целевые предпочтения, выявлены места наибольшего предпочтения гостей и туристские фирмы, предлагающие маршруты по Барнаулу. Цель исследования - выявить основные тенденции и возможности развития городского туризма в столице края и разработать проектную концепцию мероприятий, направленных на целевую аудиторию – школьников из городов и деревень Алтайского края для повышения интереса потенциальных инвесторов в развитие туристской индустрии города. Перспективы дальнейшего изучения заключаются в создании новых маршрутов в рамках городского туризма по объектам города Барнаула.

Ключевые слова: *внутренний туризм, город, городской туризм, туристский центр, туристская дестинация, детский туризм, туристские услуги*

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Introduction

A new direction for the region is urban tourism, associated with the interest of guests to travel to neighboring cities to attend events, purchase goods, as well as interest in history, architecture or art.

The flow of guests to the capital of the region increases every year (by 32% in 2022, by 7% in 2023 and amounted to 314.8 thousand people), which is associated with event, gastro-nomic, cultural and educational tourism.

The city attracts tourists from nearby

small towns – Biysk, Zarinsk, Aleisk and vil-lages, of which there are more than 1600 in the region, the main purpose of the visit is to note the need for guests to visit shopping malls, cinemas, concerts, as well as the will-ingness, with proper organization, to explore the city, get acquainted with its architecture, history, ethnicity and cultural heritage.

Over the past 10 years, the tourism sec-tor of the Altai Krai has made a qualitative and quantitative breakthrough in this direction (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 – The dynamics of the number of tourists in the Altai Krai

The districts and cities of the region pro-vide guests with all kinds of services related to urban tourism – excursions, quests, festivals, forums, holidays. There have been many bright and interesting events in the business, cultural, and sports spheres.

Based on transport accessibility, Barnaul is a transport hub on federal and regional highways and the Ob River.

There are 4,499 cultural heritage sites on the territory of the Altai Krai [9]: 2,283 histor-ical and cultural monuments of federal signif-icance, of which 2,253 are archaeological monuments, 22 are architectural monuments, 8 are historical monuments and 2,216 are of regional significance: 1,046 are monuments of the Great Patriotic War, 612 are architectural monuments, 537 are historical monuments, 18 are monuments arts.

Analysis of publications on research issues

The concept and definition of the basis of "urban tourism" appeared in Germany in 1980 by Hartmut Lezer, Heinrich Neuenfeldt and Olaf Rose [12] to more fully disclose the landmarks of tourists visiting cities for shop-ping purposes, as well as cultural, educational, and entertainment tasks.

For a real assessment of the possibilities of urban tourism development in small towns, articles by Stephen J. Page and Michael Dui-gnan [13] were analyzed, which studied the data on the results of urban tourism develop-ment by various authors since 2011 and indi-cate that little attention has been paid to it and the progress of this type of development at the present time.

Brian King, Greg Richards & Emmy Yeung [11] offer a statistical analysis of the reaction

of residents to visitors to the city, it was revealed that the city authorities are trying to diversify tourist routes for urban tourists.

L.B. Nyrenberger, N.E. Petrenko [7] analyzes the features and content of this concept and concludes that urban tourism provides an opportunity to develop other sectors of the economy, also contributes to improving the development of hotels, infrastructure, and the social sphere.

E.P. Mutavchi, L.V. Semenova [5] have revealed that this type of tourism is attractive in terms of atmosphere, individuality, traditions, values and I propose options for using the urban destination – intellectual development, relaxing holidays in parks, entertainment.

Golomidova O.Yu [2] identifies tourism as a new factor in the transformation of the urban environment and culture. Duisembayev A.A., Oralbayeva A.K., Omarkozhaeva A.N., Podsukhina O.V. [3] analyze the development of urban tourism in the Republic of Kazakhstan, consider its impact on the importance in the modern tourism industry and the possibilities of popularization.

The problems and prospects of urban tourism development in modern conditions were studied by Luchina N.A., Shchetinina N.A. [4], pointing to the specifics of the development of this type of tourism in the Russian Federation. Nikiforova A.A. [6], reveals that there is a traditional interest not only in large cities, but also in small tourist destinations, which leads to the development of infrastructure. Pavlov A.A. [8] analyzes the process of introducing information technologies into the tourism sector, which affects the development of a huge number of industries, affects the standard of living of citizens, the development of regions, contributes to job creation, affects incomes and the formation of regional budgets, helps in preserving natural and historical and cultural heritage.

Fetisova T.A., Golomidova O.Yu. [10] describe the influence of urban tourism on city residents, which helps them to be more creative in organizing routes, increases their entrepreneurial activity. Gladkiy A.V., Sklyarov A.A. [1] conclude that the formation of a tourist

urban product is necessary to meet cultural and educational needs and provides an opportunity for new jobs and income growth of the destination, but also requires qualified personnel, innovation, investment investments.

Methodology

A set of methods was used in the work: analogies, logical, system analysis, comparative, historical-geographical, statistical, economic-geographical methods. The study is based on the analysis of the assessment of official statistical data on the number of tourists, tour operators offering urban routes, information on existing elements of urban tourism in the region as a new type of tourist activity; analysis of tourist resources of Barnaul for the organization of children's urban tourism.

Researches

The development of tourism in the city of Barnaul is based on the growing demand for domestic travel in Russia. Most of the guests come from neighboring Siberian regions, followed by the large cities of Moscow, Yekaterinburg in terms of the number of tourist arrivals, Khanty-Mansiysk, Surgut, Nizhnevartovsk, Kemerovo occupy the third place. The guests are divided according to the purpose of arrival – many come for the purpose of recovery and treatment (and the main part comes 2 times a year), the main flow is business tourists, and a small part for entertainment, visiting cultural events (Fig. 2).

Fig.2 – The purpose of tourists' arrival in the city of Barnaul, %

More than 80% of vacationers arrive for a period of 2 to 4 days.

The most famous and popular among tourists are the sights associated with the

history of the Altai Krai, which are located in different districts and cities.

The city of Barnaul was built by St. Petersburg architects. Therefore, there is a certain similarity with St. Petersburg in it. It was founded in 1730 as a settlement at the Akinfiy Demidov silver smelter.

The territory of the modern Altai Krai began to be developed by the Russian state in the XVIII century. The economic and political interests of the state, which sought, on the one hand, to develop the ore riches of Altai, and, on the other, to protect the southern borders of Siberia. In the second half of the XVIII–XX centuries. Altai became the object of geographical research, which revealed its unique natural and cultural potential. Currently, the natural and cultural heritage of Altai is the most important component of tourist activity. The task of tourist organizations is to reveal as fully as possible the peculiarities of the formation and development of the territory for tourists, as well as to contribute in every possible way to the preservation of its cultural, historical and natural heritage through interaction with regional and federal authorities, as well as the media, focusing on problems and suggesting possible solutions.

In the cultural and historical heritage of Altai, a special place is occupied by the period of the XVIII - first half of the XIX centuries, known as the era of mining production or the mining period. This is the initial period of the Russian development of Altai. The time of the formation and development of the mining industry, which determined the appearance of this region for a century and a half. Thanks to state support, Altai turned into one of the leading mining regions of Russia, which used advanced technologies of that time and employed talented engineers and scientists - Ivan Polzunov, Kozma and Peter Frolov, Polycarp Zalesov, Pavel Anosov and many others. The world's largest hydraulic power plant and Russia's first railroad, created at the Zmeinogorsky mine, the world's first universal steam engine built by Ivan Polzunov in Barnaul – all these are achievements of the mining era that

glorified the Altai land. In the second half of the 19th century, with the abolition of serfdom in Russia in 1861, the mining industry of Altai, based on the serfdom system of industrial relations, entered a period of economic crisis, which ended three decades later with the closure of metallurgical enterprises.

Currently, objects of material culture of the mining era are represented in the excursion programs of Barnaul and are the most valuable sources of information for the formation of tourist interest in the historical past of Altai — this is the tourist cluster "Barnaul - mining city". The implementation of this project is connected, on the one hand, with a regional tourism policy designed to increase the attractiveness of Barnaul and the Altai Krai in the Russian tourist market, on the other hand, with the desire to preserve the cultural and historical heritage of Barnaul, represented by a number of unique objects.

Museums are called upon to play a special place in the cultural and historical space of mining Barnaul, a characteristic feature of which is their location in historical buildings of the mining era of the XVIII-XIX centuries: the museum "Mountain Pharmacy", the Altai State Museum of Local Lore, the museum "World of Stone". All the above-mentioned museums are popular objects of tourist excursion routes that reveal the theme of mining Barnaul, the mining era of Altai: Barnaul – Gornozavodskoy, The Legacy of I.I. Polzunov. The role of museums in the public life of the city is significant. The holding of the annual international action "Museum Night" shows that residents of Barnaul and guests of the regional capital are most attracted to museums located in the historical part of the city in buildings of the XVIII-XIX centuries, which organically fit in.

The number of tourists is increasing in the city of Barnaul, this is influenced by the socio-economic situation of the region (the financial ability of people from nearby territories to come only to a nearby city), but also an increase in entertainment programs, the number of shopping centers (Fig.3).

Fig.3 – Dynamics of the number of tourists in Barnaul

Let's highlight the main attractions of Barnaul.

The Upland Park is called the green zone in the center of Barnaul, on the banks of the Ob and Barnaul rivers. The park is located on a hill and rises about 30 meters above the central part of the city. In Soviet times, the VDNH exhibition worked here. It is a popular place for tourists and residents of the city to relax. It is located on a high hill with a beautiful view of the Ob River, the city and the New Bridge. The main attraction of the park is the large inscription "Barnaul" appeared back in Soviet times, when VDNH was built on the territory of the future park. The reconstruction of the park took place in 2014. The park was divided into terraces, benches and lanterns were installed, lime and cedar alleys were laid.

The embankment of the Ob River. A wide staircase leads from the Highland Park. The length of the pedestrian zone by the river is 500 meters. It is lined with paving slabs, benches are installed, above which the original lighting is equipped. Mass city events and themed festivals are often held on the stage.

Malo-Tobolskaya pedestrian street. The historic Malo-Tobolskaya Street was made pedestrian in 2017, since then the name "Barnaul Arbat" has been assigned to it. The pedestrian area was paved with paving stones, decorative fountains were installed, benches were set up, and beautiful flower beds were planted. There are many establishments with unusual cuisine and a bright atmosphere. A

sculpture of a bear has been installed, from which tourists take memorable photos.

The museum is a mountain pharmacy. The museum buildings of the XVIII century are located on Polzunov Street. Up to the 19th century, a pharmacy operated in this building, through which medicines were supplied to hospitals and hospitals. Now it is a large tourist and cultural center with historical expositions, a restaurant and a retail store where you can buy natural Altai products. The Mountain Pharmacy was built in 1752, it is the oldest preserved stone building in the city. You can also arrange a hot meal for children in the museum's restaurant by arranging it in advance.

The World of Stone Museum. The youngest museum in the city, founded only in 2010, is very popular with both Barnaul residents and tourists coming to the city. Here you can get acquainted with the amazing collection of minerals found in Altai and brought from all over the world. The exhibition presents precious and semi-precious stones, ore samples with metal inclusions, and nuggets. The collection of ancient fossils is no less impressive. In total, the museum contains more than 2 thousand exhibits. There are more than a thousand items in its collections: samples of paleobotany, ores, minerals, precious metals, decorative and precious stones, etc. In addition, the museum organizes field walking and bus tours of Barnaul. The museum aims to educate visitors in the field of geology and local history.

The Museum of Local Lore. The unique exhibits included in the collection of the museum, established back in 1823, will interest both adults and children. During the fascinating tour, you will see a lot of valuable artifacts and learn a lot of interesting things. Exhibitions of halls dedicated to ethnography talk about the life and culture of the peoples inhabiting Altai. A large exposition describes the wonderful nature of the region. There are stuffed animals and birds living in Altai, herbariums, ancient coins and decorative stone products on display. The museum's funds currently contain more than 170 thousand exhibits.

Fans of Melpomene can watch one of the magnificent performances of the Barnaul Drama Theater, established in 1921. It is located on Sakharov Square, in a beautiful building built in the middle of the last century, has a luxuriously decorated hall, bears the name of the great Russian writer, director and actor Vasily Shukshin, who was born in the Altai Krai.

Memorial of Glory. It is located on Victory Square. The architectural and monumental ensemble dedicated to the Great Patriotic War appeared on it in the 1970s. A 24-meter stele is mounted on a granite pedestal, surrounded by a concrete redoubt – a ring torn in two places. The monument is complemented by the sculpture group "Farewell", which is 6 meters high, a bowl of Eternal Flame and plates with the names of 14,000 dead soldiers. At the Memorial of Glory, students at the city's schools are worthily keeping a Memorial Watch at Post No. 1 of the city of Barnaul.

The Chocolate Museum offers exciting excursions for schoolchildren, where they will be introduced to the process of making chocolate, they will be able to taste chocolate from different parts of the world and participate in a master class and a fun quiz, and at the end receive a diploma and a sweet gift.

The museum is a city. To date, the municipal budgetary institution of the city of Barnaul "Gorod Museum" is one of the youngest museums in Barnaul, but it has an interesting history, rich collections and its own unique, well-established traditions.

Altai, along with Kuban, is considered

the main breadbasket of Russia. Therefore, it is not surprising that in the capital of the region there is a monument dedicated to the peasant and his hard work. The sculptural composition appeared on Oktyabrskaya Square of the city on September 14, 2012. The center of Oleg Zakomorny's monumental creation is the figure of a peasant and a child. The father's gaze, resting a muscular hand on his son's shoulder, is directed into the distance. A solar disk is placed behind them, against which a flock of cranes flies. This is exactly how, without fear of difficulties, peasants who were resettled from all over Russia went to Altai, hoping for a better future in this generous and fertile land.

Fort Boyard is 150 minutes of the brightest emotions and adventures created based on the popular TV show. A unique game that both adults and children will be delighted with. Children will have the opportunity to get a storm of the brightest emotions and adventures.

Barnaul Zoo is a forest fairy tale. It was officially established in 2010, but its history began much earlier, with the creation of a zoo, where residents of the city brought both domestic birds and animals, as well as abandoned and injured animals. Now, more than 350 animals of various species live on the territory of 5 hectares. There are also exotic ones among them – lions, pelicans, lynxes, marals, Himalayan bears. All animals feel great in comfortable enclosures and enjoy the guests.

Near the village of Vlasikha, you can walk around the ostrich ranch. The "highlight" of the farm are exotic ostriches. But here you can also see other animals: peacocks, camels, deer. Some of the animals are not kept in enclosures, but simply walk around the territory and are not afraid of humans at all. Both children and adults enjoy communicating with them.

The organization of urban tourism is a success among students and their parents and allows them to solve topical issues:

- to instill children's interest in the world around them, to acquire new knowledge and skills important for independence

and self-sufficiency;

- increasing the erudition of teenagers, familiarizing them with the history and culture of the region, instilling interest in the geography and history of their native land; instilling interest in the geography and history of their native land;
- formation of moral and volitional qualities of students.
- strengthening the social institution of the family, family values and traditions as the basis of the foundations of Russian society and the state.

Thus, despite the relative short duration of the hike in urban conditions, it is an effective means of educating children with a variety of knowledge, skills and abilities.

Traveling around the city, guests want to get to know it, learn about the culture, and see famous architectural structures. The tour service allows you to convey to the consumer a complex of knowledge about history, culture, geography.

The concept of the Barnaul – Gornozavodsky City tourism cluster has been developed in the Altai Krai. The historical part of the city became the object of design developments. The main task is to try to restore the historical part of Barnaul, which would be interesting and attractive for guests. The first step was the development of tourist routes around the city that arouse the interest of citizens. Barnaul has a rich history and many architectural structures. Undoubtedly, one of the pearls of the city is I. I. Polzunov Street. It

was according to her that the tour was developed – "Polzunov Street – a corner of St. Petersburg classicism". Polzunov Street is the oldest street in Barnaul, which is located in the historical part of the Central district of the city. The street received its modern name in honor of the inventor of the first steam engine, Ivan Ivanovich Polzunov, in 1947, and before that it was named Petropavlovsk, Embankment and Republic. The phrase of Fyodor Mikhailovich Dostoevsky, who visited our city twice, reads: "Barnaul is a small St. Petersburg."

St. Petersburg classicism was especially vividly and expressively demonstrated by the oldest street in Barnaul – Polzunov. Most of the buildings that made up the Peter and Paul Line ensemble are still monuments of history, science, culture and architecture, they are also objects of excursions around the city. The excursion is one of the sources of information: it is distinguished from other media (newspaper, radio, television, lecture, excursion) by its higher visibility. The tour broadens horizons, increases knowledge in the field of art, architecture, literature, and history.

Barnaul has great potential for the development of urban tourism. Many of the objects on display need restoration and the revival of their historical appearance. There are 39 tourist companies in the city that conduct city tours, but this is not profitable and makes up only a small part of their routes. Seeing the dynamics of the number of excursions, educational, cultural and historical urban tourism is popular in Barnaul (Fig.4).

Fig.4 – Dynamics of the number of excursions in Barnaul

Author's excursions and quests around the city are popular among guests and residents of the city.

An important condition for the life of a product is constant work on its improvement. The introduction of a new excursion into urban tourist routes will be an important stage in the development of tourism in the city, as urban excursions are in demand among tourists.

The name of the route: The mysteries of the city of Barnaul.

The purpose of the route: To get acquainted with new facts from the cultural and historical life of the city for schoolchildren and young people as part of organized tourism around the city.

As a result of the research of the market of tourist services, weekend tours for schoolchildren and the search for similar tourist products, it was concluded that this direction is in consumer demand.

The following companies organize school tours in Barnaul: Moy Mir tour operator, Children's Recreation and Travel Bureau, AltayTurMarket, Children's recreation Tour operator.

The main objects of urban tourism in Barnaul for showing to schoolchildren are: Nagorny Park, the Embankment of the Ob River, the City Museum, the Chocolate Museum, Ford Boyard, Ostrich Farm, the Fairy Tale Puppet Theater, the Monument to Immigrants and others.

There are 16 parks and squares in Barnaul. The largest of them are Nagorny Park, Izumrudny Park, Barnaul Arboretum, Lesnaya Skazka Park and Yubileyny Park. The city stands on the left bank of the Ob River, or rather adjoins it with its western part. There is a small reservoir (artificial) in the Emerald Park, as well as the Pivovarka River and the Barnaul River flow through the territory of Barnaul. Green spaces in Barnaul also evenly envelop all functional areas of the city. All of this can be used in urban tourism.

Barnaul city tourism is already quite an

attractive place for guests. Residents from Kazakhstan, Mongolia, and the subjects of the Russian Federation come here. Transport highways contribute to the development of business, cultural, educational, and recreational tourism. The historical part of the city of Barnaul with its architectural objects is a place to attract tourists.

Conclusions

1. Having conducted a comprehensive analysis of the development of urban tourism, consisting of an assessment of cultural and historical attractions, socio-economic condition, urban planning, infrastructure assessment, we can conclude that the potential of the city makes it possible to develop this area of tourism.

2. Having analyzed the existing resources and prerequisites for organizing an urban tourism event in the city of Barnaul, the route "Mysteries of the city of Barnaul" was developed.

3. Target audience: schoolchildren from 10 to 18 years old who are interested in urban history, architecture, who love riddles and quests; young people and couples who go to the city for concerts, entertainment, shopping malls and are ready to learn new things and visit the proposed options for excursions of urban tourism.

4. The goal is to create a positive image of Barnaul; to form a new brand of urban tourism as an affordable leisure for all segments of the population; to promote a new direction in tourism and increase awareness of both the city and the Altai Krai as a whole; to attract tourist flow to the cities of the region; to increase the interest of potential investors in the development of the tourist industry of the city.

5. The further concept of urban tourism development in Barnaul is based on the fact that the territory of the city will become a place for comfortable budget spending of guests from nearby territories and acquaintance with new interesting facts from the life of the city.

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